

An Assessment of the Efficiency of Agricultural Commodity Markets in India : Some Empirical Evidence

THOKALA SAMPATH

Abstract : *The present study is an attempt to empirically investigate the long-term market efficiency and price discovery in the Indian commodity futures market. The study has been conducted with five highly liquid commodities which include agricultural commodities. Sophisticated statistical methods like cointegration and vector error correction model (VECM) are used to analyze the spot and futures prices time series. The cointegration test shows that futures prices for all the commodities are cointegrated with the spot prices of all the commodities. The presence of short-term biases in the Indian futures market is evidenced in the results of the VECM model which indicates the presence of informational efficiency. The statistically significant value of past prices of spot and futures confirm the short-term inefficiency and biasedness. The significant value of error correction term (ECT) of futures prices suggests that commodity futures are the most important indicator of commodity price movements. The important implication of the results is for market traders. They can use the futures prices to discover the new equilibrium and earn profits by transmitting it to the spot market. A better understanding of the interconnectedness of these markets would be useful for policymakers who try to establish stability in the financial markets.*

Keywords : Agricultural commodities, Market efficiency, Spot, Futures market, Cointegration methods.

1. Introduction

The success of two economically significant positions is focused on commodity derivatives, price exploration and risk management. Numerous entities such as hedge holders, speculators and arbitrators are present on potential stocks, which implies more price seeking. Speculators usually act as equivalents to hedgers, allowing them to handle risks. In order to reap the benefit of the mispricing, referees help in seeking a better market. The commodity exchanges operate as essential locations for purchasers and sellers to perform trades with or without actual goods within a set of specified rules and regulations. Commodity exchanges are projected to lead to consumer development by reduction of transaction costs, improved price recognition and reduction of risks. Since a centralized location helps minimize expenses related to the identification of commodity content and physical examination of counterparts. Market performance is indicated by the rate and consistency at which information of asset values is conveyed.

With the introduction of futures, the same commodity is eligible for sale in both the spot and future. The dilemma here is whether demands learn information more easily. Both markets respond to information in an ideal situation. This includes the presence in commodity markets of different actors, such as growers, manufacturers, intermediaries, wholesalers, consumers, buyers, and so on. However, one market in an imperfect environment can lead another because of variations in features such as expense, liquidity, leverage and so on. The popular opinion is that futures contribute to market discovery because they take futures as a platform for their views and the related low-price advantages, as speculators and other well-known buyers. One of the key problems in India is that growers or farmers are not educated in the organized trades of commodities. Therefore, the stocks are regulated by speculators and brokers. This results in needless speculation, in turn requiring routine government action to enforce a trade embargo. It will help the potential business performance ineffectively. The research in this sense aims to quantify the performance of the commodity futures price discovery market, Lakshmi (2017).

Successful promotion of agricultural goods is pursued to safeguard the interests of both producers and customers. The forward markets commission (FMC) has needed over a decade to excel in prospective marketing. Farm production to a large degree relies on the atmosphere and the monsoon. Future trade is a methodology used for demand discovery and risk assessment in all economic fields, including producers and customers. Future exchange is a method used

for demand exploration and all segments of the economy, including producers and customers, are subject to risk management. This is seen as a weapon to avoid steep market fluctuations. Abnormal rates have a detrimental effect, with volatility, on both suppliers and customers. Future investing provides a way to measure demand and supplies over time and space, and to protect from market risks. It also provides farmers and consumers with demand cues and guidance in time.

The process of determining the spot price for a potential firm is known as “price discovery”. For two reasons, this is vital for producers. First of all, they have a clear sense of potential prevailing projected rates for commodities. Second, to maximise profit and minimise risk, they should efficiently disperse their limited wealth. Consumers frequently like becoming aware of items rates ahead of time. It is vital for a farming economy to have a well-functioning transportation system future demand in order to properly carry out the price discovery phase. The purpose of the price discovery phase is to examine if any new information has surfaced can be replicated in the future market or in adjustments in spot prices, or if the transitions between the spot and future markets are greatly delayed, Manogna and Mishra (2020). The economic transition of a developing nation such as India is crucial. It depends on the success of its agricultural sector and of its allies. In terms of rural subsistence, employment, and national food security, this sector is critical. It happens to be India’s largest source of livelihood. The proportion of the Indian population directly or indirectly relying on agriculture for employment opportunities is greater than that of any other sector in India (Economic Survey 2019-20).

Agricultural sector plays a key position in the case of the Indian economy. Farming, actively and indirectly, accounts for nearly two-thirds of the workforce. The central statistics office is projected that almost 16.5 percent of the 2019-20 gross value added at rates are estimated to be in agriculture and their relevant industries (including cultivation, animal husbandry, the forestry industry and fishing). Therefore, the Indian economy is labelled the “monsoon gamble” since the agriculture sector is highly based on monsoon. Against that background, the position of future agricultural goods contracts is much greater in an economy like India. The export of India is a major part of agricultural goods, i.e., tea, tomato, potatoes, spices, jute, cotton, peppers, coffee, sugar cane, wheat and rice. The government intervenes quite strongly in the pricing of agricultural goods since it establishes minimum rates of assistance. The method of agriculture in India has experienced dramatic changes over many decades thanks to the

implementation of green revolution technology and government policy on market subsidies (Chand, 2003). India has thus progressed from a nation with food deficits to a country with a food surplus. The government rules on the production, supply and sale of many agricultural products appear to be affected (Sahadevan, 2002). Indian farmers face every day unpredictable and crucial circumstances in the shape of the output and the price of supply. Farmers are primarily vulnerable to the danger of agricultural output and, secondly, to prices. Therefore, because of varying climatic factors, agriculture development is still full of uncertainty. In the kharif and rabi season, too the prices fluctuate. The uncertainty of markets there by causes instability immediately. In this basis, the instability affects farmers' wages, rendering rural villages poorly safe. Under all these situations, prices will fluctuate if demand decreases similarly. Future markets have two key features, namely, risk control and competition exploration, as is seen in literature (Garbade and Silber 1983).

Farmers and suppliers, though, are rather worried at potential product costs, because their vulnerability must still be mitigated by coverage. Agricultural goods need tremendously to achieve an accessible and liquid futures market in addition to improve and more reliable discovery of values. In literature, the term market discovery has been used in various ways, but the rapid incorporation of fundamental news into market pricing is critical in assessing risk. Hasbrouck (1995) described the price discovery, which is often referred to as the market share of knowledge, as the quantity by which the effective price revolution adjustment may be assigned to such a market.' As the various securities have many trading places, knowing the price discovery mechanism i.e. anything's the influence of every business to the price discovery process is essential for traders and market participants. Any farmer's primary objective is to increase his income and reduce his risk. Peak season is a big problem, with a catastrophic decline in costs. And during its season, this forces a manufacturer to sell at a lower price. When farmers want to store the selling of farm at a reasonable price for the future, they have to contend with the problems of storage depletion. In comparison, India's long intermediate chain markets are extremely fragmented and locational. Regional companies often play a dominant position and foreign players play a spoil role in these spot markets and the national markets. In the post-globalization era regional and global players on locations and domestic markets play a significant role. These market imperfections betray the aspirations of farmers, since they earn little benefit from sales of output that adversely influence their profits.

2. Review of Literature

Ali and Gupta (2011) the findings show that there is a large difference among spot and futures pricing of sugar, cashew, guar seed, pepper, red lentil, maize, chickpea, black lentil, soy bean and except two commodities wheat and rice. The findings of the Granger Causality test indicate that there is a bidirectional connecting among both commodity markets for pepper, black lentil and maize. Finally, this study found that futures market prior information comparatively spot prices. Arfaoui (2018) investigated the relationship among the both market commodities namely heating oil, gasoline propane and crude oil over a period from January 2007 to April 2015. The study employed the ARDL and ECM models to measure the relationship among the commodities. The author discovers that spot and future rates are in equilibrium over the long run. Arora and Kumar (2013) this analysis investigates the discovering costs component of metal commodities namely copper and aluminium over a period from January 2006 to December 2011. Focused on a cointegration technique, the Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) is applied. The authors concluded that order one combines both the spot and future price series and shows a stable long-run balance relationship. Chakraborty and Das (2015) the efficacy of five agricultural and three non-farming organizations, Commodities were checked by measurement of multiscale entropy, taking single and multivariate sequences. In order to calculate the performance of the Indian commodity future markets, the Multivariate Multiscale Entropy (MMSE) approach is used. The agricultural commodities chosen are barley, corn, chickpea, cumin, mustard seed and aluminium, gold, Brent crude oil are the non-agricultural commodities. The duration from 1 January 2004 to 31 December 2012 will be included. The findings show a partial performance of the Indian commodity sector. In the case of agricultural resources, productivity variations are higher. The study therefore concludes that the Indian market for products is partly efficient and that time and time scales differ in quality. Dimpfl et al. (2017) investigated the empirical relationship among the commodities prices of eight separate farm commodities such as wheat, corn, live cattle, lean hogs, feeder, soybeans, soybean meal and soybean oil. They found that both goods were special on the spot market while future markets led to price discovery by less than 10 percent.

Inani (2016) investigated the common factor models price discovery association among commodity indexes for spot markets and futures namely agriculture index, energy index, combined commodity index and metal index, The spanning period from Oct 21, 2005 to May 29, 2015, the sample includes daily closing

prices. Except for the farming index, it is observed because all indices' spot and future prices are co-integrated, they are excluded from the market discovery study. The findings show that for the combined commodity index and metal index, the discovery of prices takes place in the spot market while the discovery of prices for the energy index takes place in the futures market. Inani (2018) has been investigating, by applying Johannsen's cointegration and VECM techniques, the relation between productivity and discovery of prices in Indian agriculture products futures markets, from 1 January 2009 to 20 October 2015. The empirical results demonstrated that there is a long-term connection among spot and future agricultural commodity prices, and the pricing findings revealed that six commodities have a long-term association., including cotton seed oil cake, coriander, sugar, castor seed, turmeric, soy oil have a future demand and lead a spot market. Irafan and Hooda (2017) analyse the long-run equilibrium among the both agricultural commodities of spot and future. This research documented that there is a cointegration relationship among the whole selected farm commodities. While the Granger causality test it has been established that there is still a unidirectional flow among all agricultural commodities. Iyer and Pillai (2010) examined if a dominant position is played by futures markets method for price discovery. Two-regime autoregression threshold for calculation of chana, copper, gold, nickel, rubber and silver commodities. This study finds proof of the phase of the discovery of prices for five out of six commodities in the futures market. Joseph et al. (2014) employed frequency domain analysis, they investigated the causative relationship among the both market prices of Indian commodity markets. Their findings indicate that frequency domain analysis indicates that a clear unidirectional causation exists between both markets' commodities. Joseph et al. (2015) utilizing the wavelet study, examines the Indian futures from 2 January 2006 to 31 December 2014 on eight agricultural commodities such as gold, chana, silver, crude oil, soybean natural gas, aluminium, copper. Their findings revealed the unidirectional causative association of all chosen goods in this analysis from future markets to spot. In addition, its analytical findings indicate a strong price discovery feature on future markets and an effective future demand for Indian commodity products. Joseph et al. (2015) employed the asymmetric causality test to analyses the asymmetric causative association among the spot and future prices of farming commodities in the Indian commodity market. From January 2008 to March 2014, the data was compiled. The regular closing prices of spot and future agricultural commodities were considered to be wheat, jeera, soybean, pepper, castor seed, soy oil, coriander, cotton oilcake, chana, mustard seed and turmeric. Their results

indicate that the price discovery function is the powerful mechanism in agriculture commodity futures prices and implies the effectiveness of the potential prices of agricultural commodities in India.

Lakshmi et al. (2015) the analysis explores the connection among spot returns and contracts for the future of crude oil and gold exchanged in India for during the months of January 2005 and May 2012. The study employed the vector autoregressive model (VAR), the Granger causality test, variance decomposition and impulse response functions were used. The results have shown that the possible trading volume for both crude oil and gold is defined by its own background. Bidirectional causality takes place from gold spot to gold future selling rate. The results suggest that the rate of trade in gold goods reacts to information more easily and helps predict the return of gold in the Indian commodity markets than the return of crude oil. Lakshmi (2017) examines the long-term causal connection and path among the spot and futures markets. The cointegration test results documented that the futures causing spot in case of barley, cotton seed oilcake, Gur, mustard seed, castor seed and refined soya oil commodities. Granger causality test results documented that the bidirectional relationship in case of coriander, jeera, soya bean, sugar M grade and wheat. The study also found that there is efficiency in futures market in price discovery. Lakshmi and Joshi (2019) the research discusses the shift in the price discovery mechanism among spot and future markets for chosen inventories from the time before the crisis to the post-crisis period between November 9, 2001 and December 31, 2018. The price discovery process was studied by taking spot prices and future prices into consideration. This research uses the Johansen co-integration and the Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) in order to measure the price discovery impact since it adds to the market survey (spot or future) to minimize the possible value of knowledge. The study also extends the approach taken by Hasbrouck to exchanging information to assess the share of the price discovery contribution of each sector. The findings indicate that in the pre-crisis period there is proof of a leading potential business position. However, during the depression period, the leading role of the future disappeared. Lagesh et al. (2014) examined the potential for the advantages of portfolio diversification using estimated Dynamic Conditional Correlations in the Indian context. Empirical findings indicate that there is a very low DCC among returns from commodity futures indices and returns from conventional asset indices, which indicates the potential benefits of commodity futures for portfolio diversification.

Malhotra and Kumar (2013) in the present analysis, its efficiency and price discovery are tested using robust models such as Johansen's cointegration, Vector Error Correction process, Impulse Response and Variance Decomposition to analyse the output of the Guar seed futures market. The temporal connection among spot prices and futures prices between 2004 and 2011. Long-run co-movement is observed by spot and futures rates, and futures contracts may also work as a valuable hedging mechanism. In the short term, that there is a unidirectional flow of data from the future to the spot market i.e., the futures market is leading Guar seed to the spot market. Nair (2019) investigated the recession results in business performance of Indian-traded natural rubber futures contracts. Research reveals that the demand for rubber futures is informatively useful in discovering prices. The cointegration among the spot and future prices of natural rubber. The effect of the recession on the market effectiveness of contracts for rubber futures are evident from the rise in the optimal hedge ratios calculated using the technique of cointegration. Narsimhulu and Satyanarayana, (2016) according to the findings of this research, spot and future commodity prices have a long-term link. The outcomes of the VECM have been documented for a long-term causality ranging from future prices to spot prices. Chilli and turmeric commodity returns have unidirectional causality, whereas chana commodity futures and spot returns have bidirectional causality. Pavabutr and Chaihetphon (2010) the data collection consisting of the regular closing futures price and the exchange size between November 2003 and December 2007 of standard gold futures contracts and mini gold futures contracts is obtained from the MCX. The research used vector error correction models to explain the association among future and spot. The study finds the price of futures corresponds to spot prices, which implies that the discovery of prices takes place in the futures market.

Prasanna (2014) investigate the output of the futures market for Indian agricultural commodities over a period from March 2007 to May 2012. Study employed the Johanssen Cointegration, Granger causality and Vector error correction (VEC) models. Author observational studies have shown that spot and potential values are mixed in the long term, whereas the causality path follows twofold, unidirectional and has no reason for 11 commodities. Raghavendra et al. (2016) investigated the productivity in the commodities markets for the agriculture and future, namely turmeric, channel, soybean, corn and jeera. The study period from January 2010 to March 2015. Authors found that a long-term balance between the five spot and futures items plays a crucial

role both on the spot and potential markets in the price discovery phase. Lastly, the authors indicated that all economies are informationally productive and that markets are immediately collectively accountable. Sehgal et al. (2012) the price discovery in Indian agricultural commodity marketplaces was documented. This study has selected 10 farming products are like castor seeds, barley, soya bean, chana, maize, potato, guar seeds, kapas, pepper, and turmeric. The findings of the Johansen Cointegration Test indicate that nine out of ten commodities have a long-term balance relationship. The Granger causality test there appears to be a bidirectional relationship, according to the research spot-to-future causality for nine out of ten commodities. Overall results documented that there is no cointegration and causality relationship existed in turmeric. Shakeel and Purankar (2014) the association of prices contained in agricultural commodities would be, soya bean, castor seed and chana. The required regular data on position and commodity prices obtained from NCDEX was collected for the duration from 1 January 2009 to 31 March 2014. The findings of cointegration reveal that castor seed, chana and soya bean spot and future prices have long-term association existed. The model confirmed that the bi directionality of castor seed, chana and soya bean spot and its future sequence has led the way in India through the phase of discovery of prices, indicating the location and the chosen agricultural commodity's future markets play an important role. Sharma and Sharma (2018) the performance of Indian chilli futures markets was examined for between 2006 and 2016. The study established that chilli long-term correlation of the future and spot prices illustrated the two-way trigger of spot-future price. The findings show that both markets and errors are co-integrated. In both sectors, corrections are taking place. The outcome of the Granger causality test also supports this. Wald test results, however, show short-term causality that flows from futures to chilli spot prices. The study observes a long-run distribution among spot and futures prices suggesting that futures contracts will serve as a helpful hedging method.

Soni (2014) analysed market performance of agricultural futures contracts in India. In the time between January 2004 and September 2010. The two frameworks for study were the Johanssen co-integration and the VECM. Authors report that the future of agricultural crops is linked to their spot prices. Surobhi (2017) examined whether developments in the financialisation of agricultural commodities are evident in the Indian futures markets. During the period from July 2011 to September 2014, this study included four crops such as castor seed, guar seed, chana and soybean oil. Markets display considerably high volumes

and exchange prices in the domestic product market. The current study results show that while castor seed and soya oil undergo financialisation, Chana and guar seed tend to lend themselves to old-style speculation.

Vimal Shubhendu (2015) to investigate future-to-spot prices in seven foodstuffs such as wheat, mustard seed, chilly, jeera, pepper, castor seed and soybean. The study employed cointegration model and the “Granger causality” model. The study observational findings show the connection between future and “spot prices” and unidirectional from future market prices to spot prices for wheat, castor seed and jeera whereas the association among future market prices and spot-prices for “chilli, pepper, mustard seed and soya bean” is bidirectional. Goyari and Kumar (2011) investigated the link between the spot and futures commodities of gold, crude oil and guar seed in the context of India the time span of 2005 to 2009 by employing econometric models namely Engle-Granger Cointegration, Johansen Cointegration test, ARIMA, RW, VAR and VEC. This study discovered that the selected commodities’ futures and spot markets are both short and long-term effective. Jena and Goyari (2016) this study explored the relationship in India between the price of goods, the yield of bonds and stock prices. For three alternative asset groups from June 10, 2005 to June 30, 2011, this analysis utilises secondary data on daily returns. The analysis shows that commodity and stock prices are positively correlated, while the price of goods and the yield of bonds are negatively correlated. The conditional correlation between product prices and stock prices suggests that there is a negative correlation between both variables. If there is an elevated risk in the stock market, the conditional relationship between commodity prices and stock prices decreases, which is beneficial for investors to allocate assets to the commodity market and vice versa.

2.1. Motivation and Research Gap of the Study

The key explanation for the present objective is that comparatively numerous studies have been carried out on this topic. The present research is however, to analyse the problem and to analyse the market behaviour, in particular barley, wheat, crude palm oil, mentha oil and jeera, for the five food items chosen on the spot and for the future. Emerging markets such as India use more commodities than developing countries. The study data collected from the NCDEX and MCX. NCDEX is the agricultural commodities is one of the leading commodity exchanges of India. Different econometric models were used in the present analysis to approximate bivariate cointegration, multivariate

co-integration, causality checks and processes of error correction, among other things. That is why the analysis initially investigates whether the chosen agricultural commodities are co-integrated between the spot and future markets. The analysis is therefore verified as spot and possible co-integration are validated. We observe the interaction between the spot and future markets, nevertheless the market for few commodities such as jeera, mentha oil, barley, crude palm oil and wheat is very strong. Problems including price detection and the performance of potential product prices for commodity markets with an increased emphasis on the financial markets have been thoroughly studied. Business in emerging markets, however, and in India in particular, is restricted to the agricultural commodity markets. In this sense, this study reviews the efficiency debate on the future and spot markets of Indian agricultural commodities. The above-mentioned problems led the authors to research the efficiency of India's agricultural commodity markets.

3. Source of Data and Empirical Methodology

3.1. Data Source

This study relies on secondary data to evaluate the effectiveness of agricultural commodity futures in India. The data on daily closing prices has been collected from NCDEX and MCX. In this study the prices of five commodities such as "jeera, wheat, barley, mentha oil, and crude palm oil" and the association among spot and future markets are analyzed. The data covering the period from 1 December 2010 to 31 May 2019.

3.2. Empirical Methodology

ADF Unit Root

In order to validate integration and time-series outcomes in order of stationarity, Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF), (Dickey and Fuller, 1981) experiments have been used. The intercept and intercept and trend were used for these stationary testing, since the data span a long period of time. The ADF research lags have been calculated and the vital values in the Dickey and Fuller (1981) studies have been taken into account, depending on the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC). In the use of the time series data, first step significantly needs to verify the stationary properties of the data. The study employs the Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) test to do this. In the literature, there is a good number studies also used this model for analysis. The empirical equation is as follows

$$\Delta y_t = \alpha + \beta t + \gamma y_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^p \varpi_i \Delta y_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t$$

“Where y , β , γ , p are dependent variable, intercept in the model, linear trend in the model and integrated order of augmentation. ε is the error term in the model”.

Johansen Cointegration Test

To know the cointegration association among the variables, the present study applies Johansen cointegration model. The selected technique also extensively used in the previous empirical literature. This method works under the main assumption of vector autoregressive basis.

$$\Delta Y_t = C + \sum_{i=1}^k \Gamma_i \Delta Y_{t-1} + \Pi Y_{t-1} + \eta_t$$

Where Y_t is the variables, C is the constant in the model, k is the lag lengths in the model and Γ is the coefficients of the model. Π denotes coefficient matrix of the model and it has disintegrated as $\Pi = \alpha\beta$ are both the coefficient matrix for adjustment in the model and cointegrating vectors matrix in the model. The present method can significantly determine the number of vectors cointegrating of the model and in any given number of non-stationary data series. This technique also has another advantage is that the model can allow feedback effect among non-stationary data series. The present model is works based on likelihood ration tests that can display the number pf cointegrating vectors in the model. In addition, to determine the relationship Johansen proposed two different statistics namely trade and maximum eigen statistics in the model.

The trade statistics (test) is following as

$$\lambda_{trace} = -T \sum_{i=r+1}^n \log(1 - \hat{\lambda}_i)$$

Where T stand for number of observations of the model, $\hat{\lambda}$ donates for statistics of eigen values, η is the number of individual series of the model. Therefore,

the null hypothesis is the of long-run equilibrium cointegration vectors is $\leq r$ and where $r = 0, 1$ or 2 against the alternative hypothesis of number of long-run equilibrium cointegration of the model with vectors $= r$.

The maximum eigen test statistics is defined as

$$\lambda_{\max} = -T \log(1 - \hat{\lambda}_{r+1})$$

Here the null hypothesis is the number of long-run equilibrium cointegrating vectors $= r$ and the alternative hypothesis is the number of long-run equilibrium cointegration vectors $r + 1$. $r = 0$ is the value that tested against the alternative hypothesis which $r = 1$ and $r = 0$ is the tested against the alternative hypothesis which $r = 2$ $r = 2$. The $\lambda_{\max}$ test statistics has the sharper alternative hypothesis.

The Error Correction Method

In order to verify the causality in the long-run, if the both future and spot index level data series are stationary and non-stationary. Therefore, vector error correction technique can be used. To estimate this, the study used ECM model.

$$r_{st} = \alpha_s + \sum_{i=1}^m \beta_{si} r_{st-i} + \sum_{j=1}^m \gamma_{sj} r_{ft-i} + \lambda_s Z_{t-1} + \varepsilon_{st}$$

$$r_{ft} = \alpha_f + \sum_{i=1}^m \beta_{fi} r_{st-i} + \sum_{j=1}^m \gamma_{fj} r_{ft-i} + \lambda_f Z_{t-1} + \varepsilon_{ft}$$

In the model $Z_{t-1} S_{t-1} - \delta F_{t-1}$ is the error correction in the model with the $1 - \delta$ as long-run cointegration vectors of the model. λ_s and λ_f both are the adjustment parameters of the model.

4. Results and Discussion

To know the stationary properties of the data series and in order to achieve the study's goal. First, it is significant to avoid the problem of spurious and invalid result because these are mainly depending on non-stationary data series. To

estimate the unit root results, the study adopts Augmented Dickey Fuller test to know the order of integration. The Augmented Dickey Fuller unit root test required significant lag length, therefore, the study selected based on optimal lags which is determination of the SCI criteria. The results of time series unit root tests are displayed in Table-1. The findings of Augmented Dickey Fuller demonstration that crude palm oil future, crude palm oil spot, mentha oil future, mentha oil spot, wheat future, wheat spot, barley future, barley spot, jeera future and jeera spot variables are non-stationary at level. Therefore, it converted into first order of integration then all of the variables are stationary at their first order of integration. These results show that “crude palm oil future, crude palm oil spot, mentha oil future, mentha oil spot, wheat future, wheat spot, barley future, barley spot, jeera future and jeera spot” variables are integrated order of one, i.e. I(1).

Table 1: Unit root test results

Variables	Levels	First difference
Crude Palm Oil future	0.394 (0.797)	-47.752 (0.000) ***
Crude Palm Oil spot	0.564 (0.838)	-48.145 (0.000) ***
Mentha Oil future	0.0719 (0.705)	-44.422(0.000) ***
Mentha Oil spot	-0.788 (0.374)	-46.412 (0.000) ***
Wheat future	0.599 (0.845)	-51.230 (0.000) ***
Wheat spot	0.432 (0.807)	-14.273 (0.000) ***
Barley future	0.156 (0.731)	-45.669 (0.000) ***
Barley spot	0.254 (0.759)	-10.672 (0.000) ***
Jeera future	-0.136 (0.636)	-19.772 (0.000) ***
Jeera spot	-0.046 (0.667)	-10.934 (0.000) ***

Note: ***, indicates significance at 1% level.

In this section, the study analyses the long-run relationship among the variables. To estimates this, the study uses both bivariate and multivariate cointegration tests. The results of bivariate cointegration tests are reported in Table-2. The findings show that there is a long-run equilibrium association among crude palm oil futures, crude palm oil spots, mentha oil futures, mentha oil spots, wheat futures, wheat spots, barley futures, barley spots, jeera futures, and jeera spots. It means that these variables are cointegrating in the long-run. The results of multivariate cointegration tests are show in Table-3. The investigation also

confirmed that there is a long-term link among the variables. All the variables are moving towards the equilibrium position and it will reach same level in the long-run. Finally, the research shows that the crude palm oil future, crude palm oil spot, mentha oil future, mentha oil spot, wheat future, wheat spot, barley future, barley spot, jeera future, and jeera spot have a long-run equilibrium relationship.

Table 2: Bivariate Cointegration Results

Hypothesized: No. of CE(s)	trace test	critical values	λ -max test	critical values
Crude Palm Oil				
None	138.378	15.494***	138.375	14.264***
At most 1	0.002	3.841	0.002	3.841
Mentha Oil				
None	36.292	15.494***	31.461	14.264***
At most 1	4.8306	3.841**	4.830	3.841**
JEERA				
None	137.085	15.494***	132.750	14.264***
At most 1	4.335	3.841**	4.335	3.841**
BARLEY				
None	65.769	15.494***	62.369	14.264***
At most 1	3.400	3.841*	3.400	3.841*
WHEAT				
None	70.596	15.494***	68.635	14.264***
At most 1	1.961	3.841	1.961	3.841

“Note:***, **, * indicates significance at 1% 5% and 10% level”.

Table 3: Multivariate Cointegration Results

Hypothesized: No. of CE(s)	trace test	critical values	Prob.	λ -max test	critical values	Prob.
None	899.862	239.235	0.000***	441.375	64.504	0.000***
At most 1	458.486	197.370	0.000***	164.655	58.433	0.000***
At most 2	293.831	159.529	0.000***	85.740	52.362	0.000***
At most 3	208.091	125.615	0.000***	83.418	46.231	0.000***
At most 4	124.672	95.753	0.000***	62.643	40.077	0.000***
At most 5	62.028	69.818	0.178	26.441	33.876	0.294
At most 6	35.587	47.856	0.417	19.474	27.584	0.378
At most 7	16.112	29.797	0.704	9.780	21.131	0.764
At most 8	6.331	15.494	0.656	4.157	14.264	0.842
At most 9	2.174	3.841	0.140	2.174	3.841	0.140

Note: ***, indicates significance at 1% level.

In this section, the explore the direction of causality between crude palm oil future, crude palm oil spot, mentha oil future, mentha oil spot, wheat future, wheat spot, barley future, barley spot, jeera future and jeera spot. The result of

both causality and ECM tests are reported in Table 4. In short-run, the study finds unidirectional causality from mentha oil spot to mentha oil future. The results confirmed that jeera spot Granger causes jeera future and there is a unidirectional causality from barley spot to barley future. In the long-run, there is a bidirectional relationship between crude palm oil spot and crude palm oil future, mentha oil spot and mentha oil future, jeera spot and jeera future, wheat spot and wheat future.

Table 4: Causality and ECM Results

Hypothesis	F-statistic	Prob.	Direction
CPOS →CPOF	0.056	0.944	No Causality
CPOF →CPOS	0.247	0.780	
MOS →MOF	14.366	6.000	Unidirectional causality
MOF →MOS	3.571	0.028**	
JEERA-S →JEERA-F	4.591	0.010***	Unidirectional causality
JEERA-F →JEERA-S	198.086	4.008	
BARLEY-S →BARLEY-F	5.752	0.003***	Unidirectional causality
BARLEY-F →BARLEY-S	57.199	6.E-2	
WHEAT-S →WHEAT-F	14.746	4.000	No Causality
WHEAT-F →WHEAT-S	47.854	4.002	
Hypothesis	t-statistic	Prob.	Direction
CPOS →CPOF	-3.344	0.000***	Bidirectional causality
CPOF →CPOS	-6.023	0.000***	
MOS →MOF	-2.938	0.003***	Bidirectional causality
MOF →MOS	-9.171	0.000***	
JEERA-S →JEERA-F	-5.576	0.000***	Bidirectional causality
JEERA-F →JEERA-S	-1.701	0.088*	
BARLEY-S →BARLEY-F	-0.235	0.814	No Causality Relation
BARLEY-F →BARLEY-S	-0.712	0.475	
WHEAT-S →WHEAT-F	-2.672	0.007***	Bidirectional causality
WHEAT-F →WHEAT-S	-8.326	0.000***	

“Note: ***, **, * indicates significance at 1% 5% and 10% level”.

5. Conclusion of the Study

Furthermore, Indian agriculture responded to all the advantages in an age of globalization and liberalization. The FMC (Forward market Commission), After a lengthy embargo and rigorous laws, the Ministry of Consumer Affairs, Food,

and Public Distribution has been closely supervising the government in compliance with the Future Contracts Act 1952. Offset trading in agricultural products has been an effective forum for a variety of commodity market players in a relatively a seven-year period of time. Government played a major role in stabilizing both farmers and customers with respect to trade in agricultural goods in order to sustain the economy by minimum subsidy rates, national insurance and public distribution programmes. However, with government actions lowering demand for agricultural commodities, the futures market's role in "price discovery and price management" has become increasingly important. The feasibility of potential markets for farm crops depends on price exploration honesty and performance, agile communication demands, unjust speculation, price risk control, supply and delivery of products, infrastructure assistance etc. This study examines empirically, using the Johannsen cointegration technique, the efficiency of five key agricultural commodities that are regularly traded on NCDEX and MCX exchanges' futures markets. As evidence of empirical proof, all 5 agricultural commodities chosen "barley, jeera, crude palm oil, mentha oil, and wheat, have a long-term balance between future and spot prices".

Across the globe, day by day increasing the importance of commodity future market. It is significant for trade transactions in particularly both future and spot market. There is more problem in uncertainty to certainty. Given this background, the study considered major trading commodities for analysis. The present study examines the relationship between crude palm oil future, crude palm oil spot, mentha oil future, mentha oil spot, wheat future, wheat spot, barley future, barley spot, jeera future and jeera spot variables covering day data period from 1-12-2010 to 31-05-2019. The study applies several time series econometric methods such as unit root tests, bivariate and multivariate cointegration tests, causality and error-correction model (ECM) test. The investigation demonstrates that the variables have a long-run connection existed. The results confirmed that jeera spot granger causes jeera future and there is a unidirectional causality from barley spot to barley future. In the long-run, there is a bidirectional connection among crude palm oil spot and crude palm oil future, mentha oil spot and mentha oil future, jeera spot and jeera future, wheat spot and wheat future.

The purpose of this research is to see how efficient these agricultural commodity futures markets in India are. A well-functioning commodities futures market can provide useful signals for spot market prices while also removing the prospect of profit as part of the trading process. The equilibrium value for market

suppliers and purchasers is reflected in this futures price. The government, as well as producers and purchasers in India, are interested in studying efficiency in agricultural commodity futures markets. An effective market is a better option for the government than intervening in the market through policies. It gives processors and marketers with a solid projection of future spot pricing, allowing them to successfully manage market risks. This research can help them to get a better idea of what's going on current state of the Indian agricultural commodity futures and cash markets (H. Holly Wang and Bingfan Ke). In India, a variety of agricultural commodities are traded on many national and regional commodity exchanges, but NCDEX is the major agricultural commodity exchange. For better and more effective price discovery, an agricultural economy needs a well-functioning and for agricultural commodities, there is a liquid futures market. Despite the futures market's major role in price discovery, it can be concluded based on these findings. Furthermore, the data illustrate the amount to which "spot and futures markets contribute to price discovery" for all of the commodities studied.

For all of the commodities analyzed, the results of the stationarity and cointegration tests reveal that spot and futures prices are integrated and cointegrated at a 5% level of significance. It signifies that in its current state, the Indian commodities market is efficient, and that spot and futures prices have a long-term association. These findings also provide new insights into "price discovery" or the lead-lag association among spot and futures prices, based on relatively recent data. The findings of this study reveal that for the vast majority of commodities analysed, the futures market had a greater influence on price discovery. The current study's findings show that the futures market is more influential in the price discovery process. As a result, governments should stimulate the creation of futures markets for more agricultural commodities by enacting rules and regulations that favour the growth of futures markets (Sarveshwar Kumar Inani, 2017). India's agriculture is adapting to the era of globalization and liberalizations in order to reap the benefits. In a relatively short period of time, probably a couple of years, future trading in agricultural commodities has become an essential platform for several stakeholders in the commodity markets. The government has played a crucial role in market stabilisation in agricultural commodity markets, safeguarding both farmers and consumers through minimum support prices, market guarantee schemes, and public distribution systems. The importance of the futures market in price discovery and price management has become increasingly important as government engagement in the agricultural commodities market declines. The

viability of agricultural commodity futures markets is dependent on their transparency and efficiency of operation for price discovery, price risk management, flexible contract specification, controlling unfair speculation, commodity delivery system and coverage, infrastructural support, and other aspects.

6. Policy Implications

1. SEBI, commodities exchanges, farmers, producers, makers, brokers, and other middlemen are all interested in investigating the effectiveness of commodity futures. Based on actual evidence, SEBI and exchanges can implement improved regulatory systems and take other steps to guarantee that farmers and other beneficiaries participate actively. Setting up sophisticated infrastructure, such as good storage or warehousing facilities, standardization of norms, and so on, may entice a large number of companies to participate. (Lakshmi VDMV, 2017).
2. The price discovery association has an impact on market efficiency, policy formulation, risk management and trading tactics. The agricultural commodity futures contracts have made a substantial contribution to market information efficiency. As a result, policymakers and regulators should focus on measures that make the futures market more liquid and efficient while minimizing the impact of speculative trading.
3. Overall, the findings can assist market participants, manufacturers, dealers, wholesalers, lawmakers, regulators, and researchers in determining the efficiency of agricultural commodity futures contracts. The findings would help market participants by allowing them to develop effective trading methods that would eventually lead to arbitrage and hedging are two methods for reducing financial risk.

7. Limitations of the study

1. The study's first limitation is the small sample size of only five commodities. It's because we've just looked at the top five most liquid commodities. Because of data limitations, only the Indian agricultural commodity market was considered.
2. Daily closing prices, both spot and futures, were used in the study, however intra-day data might be used to obtain more precise results. The study focused on only five agricultural commodities, while NCDEX trades a wide range of agricultural goods.

8. Future Research or Scope of Research

1. Analyzing the factors that influence agricultural commodity price discovery in various nations could be a valuable study topic in the near future.
2. Rainfall, seasons, and government assistance in the form of subsidies and support prices are all important factors in agricultural commodities.
3. It's also possible to do similar study and evaluate the results on other national commodities markets including the MCX, NMCE, ICEX, and UCEA variety of natural elements, such as harvest-dependent seasonal cycles, monsoons, depressions, and weather-related events, which is another area that requires further investigation.

References

- Ali, J., & Gupta, K. B. (2011). Efficiency in agricultural commodity futures markets in India. *Agricultural Finance Review*.
- Arfaoui, M. (2018). On the spot-futures relationship in crude-refined petroleum prices: New evidence from an ARDL bounds testing approach. *Journal of Commodity Markets*, 11, 48-58.
- Arora, S., & Kumar, N. (2013). Role of futures market in price discovery. *Decision*, 40(3), 165-179.
- Chakraborty, R., & Das, R. (2015). A Multivariate Multiscale Entropy Approach to Testing Commodity Market Efficiency. *IUP Journal of Financial Risk Management*, 12(3).
- Dimpfl, T., Flad, M., & Jung, R. C. (2017). Price discovery in agricultural commodity markets in the presence of futures speculation. *Journal of Commodity Markets*, 5, 50-62.
- Goyari, P., & Kumar Jena, P. (2011). Commodity Futures Market in India: An Econometric Analysis. *Indian Journal of Economics*, 91(363), 699.
- Inani, S. K. (2016). Price discovery in Indian commodity market. *International Journal of Business and Emerging Markets*, 8(4), 361-382.
- Inani, S. K. (2018). Price discovery and efficiency of indian agricultural commodity futures market: an empirical investigation. *Journal of Quantitative Economics*, 16(1), 129-154.
- Inoue, T., & Hamori, S. (2014). Market efficiency of commodity futures in India. *Applied Economics Letters*, 21(8), 522-527.

- Irafan M and Hooda J (2017) An Empirical Study of Price Discovery in Commodities Futures Market, *Indian Journal of Finance*, 11, (13), 41-57.
- Iyer, V., & Pillai, A. (2010). Price discovery and convergence in the Indian commodities market. *Indian Growth and Development Review*.
- Jena, P. K., & Goyari, P. (2016). Empirical Relationship between Commodity, Stock and Bond Prices in India: A DCC Model Analysis. *IUP Journal of Applied Finance*, 22(1), 37.
- Joseph, A., Sisodia, G., & Tiwari, A. K. (2014). A frequency domain causality investigation between futures and spot prices of Indian commodity markets. *Economic Modelling*, 40, 250-258.
- Joseph, A., Sisodia, G., & Tiwari, A. K. (2015). The inter-temporal causal nexus between Indian commodity futures and spot prices: A wavelet analysis. *Theoretical Economics Letters*, 5(02), 312.
- Joseph, A., Suresh, K. G., & Sisodia, G. (2015). Is the causal nexus between agricultural commodity futures and spot prices asymmetric? Evidence from India. *Theoretical Economics Letters*, 5(02), 285.
- Kaur, G., & Dhiman, B. (2019). Agricultural Commodities and FMCG Stock Prices in India: Evidence from the ARDL Bound Test and the Toda and Yamamoto Causality Analysis. *Global Business Review*, 0972150919830803.
- Lagesh, M. A., Kasim C, M., & Paul, S. (2014). Commodity futures indices and traditional asset markets in India: DCC evidence for portfolio diversification benefits. *Global Business Review*, 15(4), 777-793.
- Lakshmi, P., Visalakshmi, S., & Padmavathy, S. (2015). Exploring the nexus between futures contracts and spot returns in the Indian commodity market. *International Journal of Indian Culture and Business Management*, 10(3), 306-317.
- Lakshmi, V. D. M. V. (2017). Efficiency of Futures Market in India: Evidence from Agricultural Commodities. *IUP Journal of Applied Economics*, 16(3).
- Lakshmi, V. D. M. V., & Joshi, M. (2019). Price Discovery Behaviour of Spot and Futures: Evidence from Pre-and Post-Crisis Periods. *IUP Journal of Applied Economics*, 18(4).
- Malhotra, M., & Kumar Sharma, D. (2013). Efficiency of Guar Seed Futures Market in India: An Empirical Study. *IUP Journal of Applied Finance*, 19(2).
- Manogna, R. L., & Mishra, A. K. (2020). Price discovery and volatility spillover: an empirical evidence from spot and futures agricultural commodity markets in India. *Journal of Agribusiness in Developing and Emerging Economies*.

- Nair, S. T. G. (2019). Recession effect in pricing efficiency of rubber futures: the emerging market's experience. *Journal of Agribusiness in Developing and Emerging Economies*.
- Narsimhulu, S., & Satyanarayana, S. V. (2016). Efficiency of Commodity Futures in Price Discovery and Risk Management: An Empirical Study of Agricultural Commodities in India. *Indian Journal of Finance*, 10(10), 7-26.
- Pavabutr, P., & Chaihetphon, P. (2010). Price discovery in the Indian gold futures market. *Journal of Economics and Finance*, 34(4), 455-467.
- Prasanna, G. S. (2014). Performance Evaluation of Agricultural Commodity Futures Market in India. *IUP Journal of Applied Finance*, 20(1), 34.
- Raghavendra, R. H., Velmurugan, P. S., & Saravanan, A. (2016). Relationship between spot and futures markets of selected agricultural commodities in India: an efficiency and causation analysis. *Journal of Business & Financial Affairs*, 5(1), 2167-0234.
- Ranganathan, T., & Ananthakumar, U. (2014). Market efficiency in Indian soybean futures markets. *International Journal of Emerging Markets*.
- Sehgal, S., Rajput, N., & Dua, R. K. (2012). Price discovery in Indian agricultural commodity markets. *International Journal of Accounting and Financial Reporting*, 2(2), 34.
- Shakeel, M., & Purankar, S. (2014). Price discovery mechanism of spot and futures market in India: A case of selected agri-commodities. *International Research Journal of Business and Management*, 8(8), 50-61.
- Sharma, P., & Sharma, T. (2018). A Study of the Efficiency of Chili Futures Market in India. *IUP Journal of Financial Risk Management*, 15(3), 32-43.
- Soni, T. K. (2014). Cointegration, linear and nonlinear causality. *Journal of Agribusiness in Developing and Emerging Economies*.
- Surobhi, M. (2017). Futures markets-old style speculation or financialisation? *Economic and Political Weekly*, 52(35).
- Vimal Shubhendu (2015) Testing Efficiency in Agricultural Commodity Futures Market in India Using Cointegration and Causality Tests, *Indian Journal of Finance*, 9,(12), 51-62.